

Combining chromatographic and spectroscopic fingerprinting with chemometrics and data fusion to characterize the phytochemical composition of anthocyanin-rich fruit extracts

Ance Bārzdina^{a,b,*} , Daniela Paula Prudņikova^{a,b}, Marta Žogota^c, Baiba Mauriņa^{b,d}, Dace Bandere^{a,b}, Agnese Brangule^{a,b}

^a Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Riga Stradins University, 21 Konsula Str, LV-1007 Riga, Latvia

^b Baltic Biomaterials Centre of Excellence, Headquarters at Riga Technical University, 3 P Valdena Str, LV-1007 Riga, Latvia

^c Laboratory of Finished Dosage Forms, Faculty of Pharmacy, Riga Stradins University, 21 Konsula Str, LV-1007 Riga, Latvia

^d Department of Applied Pharmacy, Riga Stradins University, 21 Konsula Str, LV-1007 Riga, Latvia

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ABSTRACT

Due to high visual similarity, rich anthocyanin content, drastically different availability, and wide use in the pharmaceutical and food industries, products that contain fruits of the genus *Vaccinium* can become targets of adulteration. This study aimed to obtain phytochemical fingerprints of two anthocyanin-rich fruit extracts (highbush blueberry and bilberry) using four different analytical techniques (HPLC-UV; HPLC-MS/MS; FTIR; UV/Vis) and explore the relationships and similarities of the chemical compositions by applying chemometric data analysis (PCA and PLS-DA) combined with low-level and mid-level data fusion approaches. Tentative identification with subsequent quantification of polyphenols found in these extracts was performed using HPLC-MS/MS analysis. To test the application of mid-level data fusion combined with chemometrics, mixed extracts containingighbush blueberry as well as bilberry extracts were prepared and analyzed. Highbush blueberry lyophilized extracts contained roughly 5 times more chlorogenic acid than bilberry extracts, while bilberry extract showed higher concentrations of anthocyanins and caffeic acid. Both extracts had highly similar spectroscopic fingerprints. After mid-level data fusion, an optimized PLS-DA model with 75 observations (65 pure extract samples, 10 mixed extract samples) and 7 key variables (first principal components of all analysis) was developed (R^2_X 0.950, R^2_Y 0.949, and Q^2 0.941). This model allows to correctly classify pure extracts from mixed extracts, but cannot differentiate between different ratios of mixes. Combining fingerprinting information with mid-level data fusion can simplify the model while still accurately representing the key features of phytochemical fingerprints and is worth examining as a tool for the detection of anthocyanin-rich extract adulterations in the future.

1. Introduction

Natural products, including herbal extracts, have been a cornerstone of healthcare for centuries, both as prophylactic and therapeutic agents for patients of all ages. The global herbal medicine market exceeds US \$60 billion annually with exponential growth (Ahmad Khan and Ahmad, 2019). Moreover, up to 40 % of medicines on the market today have originated either directly or indirectly from natural products (Calixto, 2019). Plant extracts rich in polyphenols are known for their wide spectrum of pharmacological activity, including antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and even anti-neoplastic (Bolat et al., 2024).

Moreover, in general society, natural products are associated with lower toxicity and fewer side effects (Barry, 2018; Goodarzi et al., 2013).

However, the lack of regulations regarding herbal medicines makes contamination and adulteration a serious and ever-increasing problem (Posadzki et al., 2013). The identification of the composition of natural products is burdened by the complex phytochemical composition consisting of hundreds to thousands of chemical compounds. Moreover, climate and growth factors like temperature, humidity, and soil composition can significantly impact the phytochemical composition, making standardization and quality control a challenge (Tiwari and Cummins, 2013).

* Corresponding author at: Riga Stradins University, 16 Dzirciema Str, LV-1007 Riga, Latvia.

E-mail address: ance.barzdina@rsu.lv (A. Bārzdina).

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Since the contamination and/or adulteration of natural products can lead to serious adverse effects, in-depth research on methods to sufficiently and precisely detect such malpractices is mandatory. One such method that is generating more and more attention is phytochemical fingerprints. Instead of identifying a single marker, fingerprinting methods use the whole chemical profile or extract the parts of the profile responsible for characteristic parameters of the product, allowing it to both identify the product and characterize its quality (Bārzdīņa et al., 2022; Brangule et al., 2020; Noviana et al., 2022). Since many of the phytochemical compounds can act synergically to produce a pharmacological activity, taking into consideration the whole chemical profile is superior to determining only a single compound (Noviana et al., 2022). Herbal fingerprinting has proven particularly useful for herbal product quality analysis (Li et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2024).

Anthocyanin-rich extracts are notoriously hard to analyze due to the similarities of the phytochemical compounds and profiles. Anthocyanins give the extracts their characteristic color, sometimes further limiting or hindering chemical analysis. The genus *Vaccinium* belongs to the Ericaceae family and contains fruit-producing shrubs like cranberries, lingonberries, blueberries, and bilberries (J. Johnson et al., 2010; Martáu et al., 2023). The fruits of the Genus *Vaccinium* contain significant amounts of anthocyanins and other polyphenols like phenolic acids (Martáu et al., 2023; Tundis et al., 2021). Moreover, the fruits are widely used in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

Due to the high visual similarity but drastically different availability and value, fruits of two species of Genus *Vaccinium* – *Vaccinium myrtillus* (bilberry) and *Vaccinium corymbosum* (highbush blueberry) – were selected for this study.

V. myrtillus is a dwarf shrub commonly found in forests with acidic and well-drained soil found in northern parts of North America and Europe (Tundis et al., 2021). The fruits of this shrub have a long-standing use in traditional medicine, with acknowledged health benefits by the European Pharmacopoeia and European Medicines Agency (EMA) (*Herbal medicine: summary for the public. Fresh bilberry fruit*, 2015; Pharmacopoeia, 2020). Thanks to their beneficial health properties, bilberries and their extract are widely used in the food and pharmaceutical industries, mainly in the form of food or dietary supplements (Gaspar et al., 2021; Pires et al., 2020). Only a few other medicinal plants can compete with bilberries regarding anthocyanin content (Bayazid et al., 2021; Chu et al., 2011; Martáu et al., 2023). Because of the high anthocyanin content, bilberry extract is one of the most expensive natural products (Gardana et al., 2014, 2018; Govindaraghavan, 2014). Due to deforestation and climate change, the yield of these berries is decreasing. Therefore, bilberry products are becoming targets of adulteration and malpractice. Bilberry products are mostly adulterated with anthocyanin-rich, lower-cost fruits from other species, often from the same genus *Vaccinium* (Gafner, 2015; Govindaraghavan, 2014; Hellström et al., 2024; Lee, 2016; Primetta et al., 2013).

Thanks to agricultural advantages, sweet taste, and an esthetically pleasing look, highbush blueberries have become one of the most popular, highly produced, and well-liked fruits used today (Martáu et al., 2023; Tran and Tran, 2021; Tundis et al., 2021). However, the phytochemical composition and pharmacological activity of highbush blueberry products are still insufficiently examined. Due to their lower cost, highbush blueberries and their extracts are one of known bilberry adulterants (Gafner, 2015). Moreover, the chemical profile of highbush blueberries is very similar to that of bilberries (Gafner, 2015).

Distinguishing these two species using basic organoleptic or simple stand-alone analytical methods like thin-layer chromatography may be difficult (Gafner, 2015). If the identification of fresh fruit for an expert is not hindered, when the fruits are processed into extracts, powders, food supplements, and other types of products, the task becomes increasingly harder. Even Pharmacopoeial HPLC methods have been suggested as not sufficient to detect adulterations of bilberry extracts (Govindaraghavan, 2014). Therefore, the phytochemical profiles of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts, using an array of analytical methods that are accessible

and commonly used by the pharmaceutical industry and regulatory instances, should be obtained and inspected. Moreover, using a combination of analytical techniques allows us to characterize the complexity of natural products in much more detail and is superior to using just a single method (Xu et al., 2023).

This study aimed to obtain phytochemical fingerprints of anthocyanin-rich fruit extracts (highbush blueberry and bilberry) using four different analytical techniques (high-performance liquid chromatography equipped with a UV detector (HPLC-UV); high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS); Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR); ultraviolet/visible light spectroscopy (UV/Vis)) and explore the relationships and similarities of the chemical compositions by applying chemometric data analysis combined with low-level and mid-level data fusion approaches. For chemometric analysis, principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least squares-discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) were performed. Chemometric analysis was applied separately to characterize relationships between the species and their chemical composition and to analyze low-level and mid-level fused data. In addition, tentative identification with subsequent quantification of polyphenols found in these extracts was performed using HPLC-MS/MS analysis. Mixed extracts, which contain both highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts in various ratios, were prepared and analyzed to test the wider applicability of the chosen approach.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

A total of 17 fresh highbush blueberry samples were obtained from local farmers from various regions of Latvia (Talsi, Aizkraukle, Valmiera, Cēsis, Bauska, Dobeles, Smiltene, and Jēkabpils municipalities) in early August of 2022 and 2024. A total of 9 bilberry samples were obtained from forests in Latvia (Talsi, Bauska, Smiltene, and Jēkabpils municipalities) in late July of 2022 and 2024. After macroscopic evaluation, berry samples were stored in sealed containers at -20°C . For each sample, a code was generated. The code stands for the type of berry and the sample number. COR stands for *V. corymbosum* (highbush blueberry) samples. MYR stands for *V. myrtillus* (bilberry) samples. These codes are applied throughout the whole study. Voucher samples are stored in an internal collection of the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry of Riga Stradins University.

2.2. Reference standards

A total of 10 reference standards were used: Chlorogenic acid (European Pharmacopoeia reference standard), caffeic acid ($\geq 98\%$ (HPLC)), p-coumaric acid ($\geq 98\%$ (HPLC)), ferulic acid (secondary pharmaceutical standard), kaempferol ($>97\%$ (HPLC)), quercetin ($>95\%$ (HPLC)), syringic acid (analytical standard) were bought from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside chloride (primary reference standard), gallic acid (primary reference standard), and rutin (primary reference standard) were bought from PhytoLab (Vestenbergsgreuth, Germany). All other reagents were of analytical grade.

2.3. Preparation of lyophilized extracts

The frozen berries were thawed at room temperature for several hours before further processing. Thawed berry samples were homogenized using a hand blender. Ethanol extracts were prepared using 96.2% ethanol (v/v) using the maceration method for 24 h. The sample to ethanol ratio was 1:10 (w/v). After extraction, the obtained extracts were filtered (grade 3-HW filter paper, Sartorius (Göttingen, Germany)), and the supernatant was collected. To remove ethanol from the collected supernatant, rotary vacuum evaporation at 60°C was applied until a thick mass remained. Further, the evaporated extracts were frozen at

–80 °C for 24 h with subsequent freeze drying for 24 h at –80 °C and 0.05 mbar pressure. The obtained lyophilized extracts were stored in sealed containers at +4 °C until further analysis. Extract preparation was executed in triplicate for all samples to test the reproducibility of the extract preparation and applied analytical processes. That resulted in a total of 78 extracts prepared.

2.4. HPLC-UV

Lyophilized extracts were dissolved in 50 % acetonitrile to obtain a concentration of 10 mg/mL. The solutions were filtered through 0.45 µm syringe filters before analysis.

HPLC-UV analysis was performed on a DIONEX UltiMate 3000 UHPLC+ focused system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Ascentis Express 90 Å AQ-C18 column (15 cm × 3.0 mm, 2.7 µm, Supelco, Darmstadt, Germany) was used. The mobile phase was composed of 0.1 % aqueous trichloroacetic acid (v/v) (A) and acetonitrile (B) with the following gradient: 0 min – 5 % B, 10 min – 15 % B, 30 min – 35 % B, 33 min – 90 % B, 35 min – 5 % B. A 4-minute equilibration phase using 5 % B was performed before each analysis. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min, method length 35 min, column temperature 40 °C, injection volume 1 µL. The absorption was measured at 3 different wavelengths – 280 nm, 360 nm, and 520 nm.

The chromatogram section from 4 min to 25 min (280 nm and 360 nm) and from 12 min to 22 min (520 nm) was chosen as the fingerprint region and used in further data analysis. Peaks before 4 min and after 25 min were discarded due to the possibility of false signals unrelated to the polyphenolic composition of the sample. For chromatograms obtained at 520 nm peaks were observed only in the region 12 min to 22 min; therefore, the rest was excluded from data processing. For each type of herbal extract (highbush blueberry and bilberry) at all 3 wavelengths an average chromatogram was created. Chromatograms were used for chemometric analysis, data fusion, and qualitative identification of key components. Normalized vs non-normalized chromatograms were compared using chemometric analysis.

For the initial qualitative screening of the chemical composition of extracts, the retention times of peaks were compared to those of the following reference standards - chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, p-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, kaempferol, quercetin, syringic acid, cyanidin-3-O-glucoside chloride, gallic acid, and rutin. In-depth identification and quantification of polyphenols were performed using HPLC-MS/MS.

2.5. HPLC-UV method assessment

The suitability of the HPLC-UV method for fingerprinting purposes was assessed in terms of a calibration curve, repeatability, intermediate precision, and recovery. Since the whole fingerprint region, not individual compounds, would be used in chemometric analysis and data fusion,ighbush blueberry extract was used for the method assessment. Chlorogenic acid reference standard as a dominant compound ofighbush blueberry extract was chosen to spike the extract in recovery analysis and obtain the calibration curve.

The calibration curve was obtained using chlorogenic acid solutions in ethanol. A stock solution of 100 µg/mL was diluted to obtain 6 more concentrations (80 µg/mL, 60 µg/mL, 40 µg/mL, 20 µg/mL, 10 µg/mL, 1 µg/mL). The wavelength was set to 280 nm. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting the peak area against the concentration of the standard solutions. The results were linear with the obtained regression equation $y = 0.068x - 0.0849$ and a correlation coefficient of 0.9996.

Repeatability was analyzed by injecting 10 mg/mL ofighbush blueberry extract six times on the same day. The chromatograms of the chosen fingerprint region were used for calculation of Pearson's correlation coefficient, using the Origin Pro 2023 software. Pearson's correlation coefficient of these injections was calculated to be 0.9945.

Intermediate precision was determined by injecting 10 mg/mL of theighbush blueberry extract three times on two consecutive days. The

sample preparation and chromatographic analysis were executed by another operator. Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated for the whole chromatograms of the chosen fingerprint region. Pearson's correlation coefficient of these injections was calculated to be 0.9343.

Recovery was determined by spiking aighbush blueberry extract with 100 µg/mL, 80 µg/mL, and 60 µg/mL solutions of chlorogenic acid reference standard. Each sample was analyzed in triplicate. The recovery of chlorogenic acid was higher than 96.7 %.

The results of the method validation were satisfactory, therefore indicating that the method is applicable for the fingerprinting analysis of extracts used in this study.

2.6. HPLC-MS/MS

The samples for HPLC-MS/MS analysis were prepared the same as for HPLC-UV analysis (see Section 2.4). HPLC-MS/MS was used for qualitative and quantitative analysis of theighbush blueberry and bilberry extracts in addition to chemometric analysis and data fusion. HPLC – MS/MS analysis was performed following a previously published method by Zolotova et al. with slight modifications (Zolotova et al., 2024). Since anthocyanin-rich extracts are notoriously hard to analyze due to the similarity of various compounds, which makes adequate separation a challenge, two variations of a method were used in this study – one for overall polyphenol analysis, the other for specifically anthocyanins. The difference between these versions is the concentration of formic acid in the mobile phase.

The HPLC-MS/MS analysis was performed on a Vanquish Core HPLC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Zorbax Eclipse Plus, C18, 2.1 × 150 mm, 5 µm, column was used. In the overall polyphenol method, the mobile phase was composed of 0.1 % formic acid (v/v) (A) and 0.1 % formic acid in acetonitrile (B). In the anthocyanin method, the mobile phase was composed of 1 % formic acid (v/v) (A) and 1 % formic acid in acetonitrile (B). Both methods followed the same gradient: initial 5 % B, 0–2 min 5 % B, 2–7 min 20 % B, 7–10 min 45 % B, 10–15 min 95 % B; 15–20 min 95 % B, 20–22 min 5 % B. The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min, method length 22 min, sampler temperature 10 °C, column compartment temperature 40 °C. The injection volume was 3 µL.

Mass spectrometric analysis was executed on Orbitrap Exploris™ 120 mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) equipped with a heated electrospray ionization (HESI-II) probe (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Positive ion mode with the scan range (m/z) of 100 to 1500 was used. The main mass spectrometer's settings were: resolution 60,000, spray voltage +3500 V/–2500 V; sheath gas flow rate 50 Arb, auxiliary gas flow rate 10 Arb; Ion Transfer tube temperature 325 °C; vaporizer temperature 350 °C; HCD collision energy 30 %.

The data were acquired using Thermo Scientific XCalibur 4.6.67.17 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.; Waltham, MA, USA) and processed using Thermo Scientific Trace Finder™ 5.1 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.; Waltham, MA, USA) based on own and internet databases: Mass Bank of North America (Davis, CA, USA), m/z Cloud (HighChem; Bratislava, Slovakia), FooDB (project supported by the Canadian Institutes of Health Research, Canada Foundation for Innovation, and by The Metabolomics Innovation Centre (TMIC)). The phytochemicals present in the extracts were identified based on data available in the literature, utilizing exact molecular mass, characteristic fragmentation ions, and retention time. To quantify the polyphenolic compounds of interest, the calibration curves of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, rutin, p-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, quercetin, kaempferol, and cyanidin-3-O-glucoside reference standards were obtained. The identified tentative compounds were expressed as the corresponding compounds or their equivalents.

Base peak chromatograms from both methods were used for chemometric analysis. The section from 0 min to 16 min was selected for both polyphenol and anthocyanin methods as the fingerprint region and used in subsequent chemometric analysis. An average base peak chromatogram for each type of extract was generated. For chemometric

analysis and data fusion, the chromatograms were normalized.

2.7. FTIR

An iS5 FTIR spectrometer with an iD7 ATR device (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and the OMNIC software were used for ATR-FTIR analysis. Lyophilized extracts were analyzed in the spectral range of 450–4000 cm^{-1} using 16 scans per sample and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The region of 500 cm^{-1} to 1800 cm^{-1} was chosen as the fingerprint and used for chemometric analysis. For chemometric analysis and data fusion, the obtained spectra were normalized, and the average spectra for both types of extracts were generated. Spectra derivatization was not applied in this study to minimize the chance of formation of artifacts, alleviate spectra interpretation, and facilitate further analysis.

2.8. UV/Vis spectrophotometry

The samples for UV/Vis analysis were prepared by diluting the 10 mg/mL samples in 50 % acetonitrile (as prepared for HPLC-UV) 1:50 for highbush blueberry extracts and 1:100 for bilberry extracts. UV/Vis spectra were obtained in the region 190 nm to 800 nm. Measurements were executed on a Mettler-Toledo UV7 spectrophotometer (Mettler-Toledo International Inc. Greifensee, Switzerland). For fingerprint analysis, the obtained spectra were normalized, and the average spectra for both types of extracts were generated. The region from 195 nm to 600 nm was chosen for chemometric analysis and data fusion.

2.9. Chemometric analysis

Out of a total of 78 extracts prepared, 3 were excluded due to inadequate freeze-drying process, therefore, a total of 75 samples were subjected to chemometric analysis. SpectraGryph 1.2.17. software (Friedrich Menges, Oberstdorf, Germany) (Menges, 2024) was used to separate the chosen fingerprint regions, normalize the data, correct the baseline, and generate the average chromatograms or spectra of the obtained data from all analytical techniques. Data normalization allows the standardization of data based on the pattern of the whole chromatogram or spectra and does not take into consideration variations in concentrations of different compounds due to the climate, soil, and other factors. Data normalization was applied for all data used for chemometric analysis in this study. Data were normalized using the peak normalization function in the SpectraGryph software, where the highest peak is set to the value of 1. The processed spectra or chromatograms were exported as .dat files for further analysis. Pearson's correlation coefficients of analyzed data were obtained using the OriginPro 2023 software.

Since all the analytical methods produce substantial amounts of data, it is possible to decrease the vast volume of data and extract information and features of interest by using multivariate statistical analysis techniques (Cornejo-Báez et al., 2020). Two types of multivariate analysis – PCA and PLS-DA – were applied in this study.

PCA was used to characterize the relationships between the chemical profiles of extracts using all four analytical techniques separately, as well as a tool for low and mid-level data fusion (see Section 2.10). PCA is a non-supervised multivariate analysis technique that finds and interprets the similarities and differences of samples and allows to explain the properties of key elements of the chemical composition responsible for the clustering of samples (Arumugam et al., 2012; Cornejo-Báez et al., 2020). The results of the PCA were analyzed by determining the total % of explained variance of the model and visualized using score scatter plots.

PLS-DA is a supervised, linear discriminant analysis technique that provides sample categorization into classes that can be used as an interpretation model, as well as a prediction tool (Galindo-Prieto et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2018; Obisesan et al., 2017; Ruiz-Perez et al., 2020; Zhang and Wang, 2023). It is become one of the most commonly used

methods applied to fused data for qualitative analysis of medicinal plants (Zhang and Wang, 2023). In this study PLS-DA analysis was applied only for mid-level fused data analysis.

PCA and PLS-DA were performed using SIMCA 17 software (Umetrics, Umea, Sweden).

2.10. Data fusion

To see if these analytical methods can be used not only as standalone techniques but also in conjunction with one another, two data fusion approaches – low-level and mid-level – were performed for the obtained data. The data fusion followed by chemometric analysis was executed on the SIMCA software. Low-level fusion relies on a mechanical concatenation of data from multiple analytical methods into one new larger data matrix (Zhang and Wang, 2023). To do that, the data must be measured on a similar scale for successful concatenation. In this study, low-level data fusion was executed on the HPLC-UV data from all three wavelengths alone and the HPLC-MS/MS data (both methods) together with all the HPLC-UV data. All HPLC data was on the same scale and the data was normalized, therefore, low-level data fusion was possible. A top-bottom merging function was used, and the data was merged based on the primary variable ID. Subsequently, PCA analysis on the merged datasets was performed.

To further add spectroscopic data to the data fusion and extract the most important features from each of the methods, mid-level data fusion was performed. In mid-level data fusion, the fused dataset consists of extracted features from individual datasets, therefore reducing the volume of the data while increasing result interpretability (Zhang and Wang, 2023). Firstly, the scores of the first five PCs of PCA analysis of each of the analytical methods used were exported for all samples. The first five PCs were chosen since in all methods, these 5 combined principal components (PCs) explained >70 % of the variance. Next, a dataset consisting of all observations (75 samples) and variables (35 PC scores) was created. The dataset was randomly divided into two parts – a training set consisting of 65 observations and a prediction set consisting of 10 observations (5 from highbush blueberries, 5 from bilberries). The data were categorized into two classes – highbush blueberry extracts (1) and bilberry extracts (2). PLS-DA analysis was performed on the model training set, using cross-validation while fitting with 7 cross-validation groups. The VIP (variable importance for the projection) values were analyzed to see which variables were most important to explain the observations and predict the class. Only variables with values above 1 were chosen for further analysis. PLS-DA analysis was executed on all the observations of the training set using the variables with the most importance, using the same cross-validation parameters. The model was evaluated based on the separation of scores scatter plot, R^2 (cumulative), and Q^2 (cumulative) values. To test the developed model, the assignment to classes was predicted for the set of 10 observations that were not included in the building of the model. The accuracy of the prediction was assessed.

2.11. Mixed samples

To test the application of the fingerprinting methods and developed data fusion model for the determination of adulterated samples, mixed extracts were made. Mixed extracts were prepared by randomly selecting and combining the prepared highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts in weight ratios 20:80, 40:60, 50:50, 60:40, and 80:20. Three mixed samples were prepared for each type of ratio; therefore, the total number of mixed extracts was 15. The mixed samples were tested by all four analytical methods – HPLC-UV, HPLC-MS/MS, FTIR and UV/Vis to obtain fingerprints. The sample preparation and data processing of mixed samples was the same as for single extracts, except for UV/Vis analysis a dilution of 1:75 was applied for adequate absorption measurements. First, PCA analysis was performed for all samples (single extracts and mixed extracts) for each analytical method. Then data

fusion to data from all four analytical methods was applied as previously described. 10 samples from the mixed extracts were added to the training set group and 5 to the prediction set. The rest of the PLS-DA model was built the same way as described in Section 2.10. A total of three model versions were compared – 3 classes, 5 classes, and 7 classes – to assess how accurately the models can predict adulterated (in our case – mixed) samples. The assignment to classes of all the samples for all three model versions can be found in Fig. 1.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. HPLC-UV fingerprints and their chemometric analysis

The obtained HPLC-UV fingerprints of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts at 280 nm, 360 nm, and 520 nm can be found in Fig. 2. The respective wavelengths were chosen due to the absorption maxima of phenolic acids (280 nm), flavonoids (360 nm), and anthocyanins (520 nm) (Aleixandr-Tudo and Toit, 2018).

Highbush blueberry extract chromatograms at 280 nm and 360 nm indicate that the dominant compound could be chlorogenic acid with a retention time of 9.8 min (Fig. 2A) since the standard solution of chlorogenic acid showed the same retention time. The chlorogenic acid peak is not as prominent in bilberry extracts; however, peaks in bilberry extract chromatograms indicate a much higher overall flavonoid, including anthocyanin, concentrations (Fig. 2). The high-anthocyanin content of both of these extracts influences the chromatograms not only at 520 nm but also at 280 nm due to anthocyanins having two absorption maxima – one in the visible light range (510–530 nm) and one in the ultraviolet light range (270–280 nm) (Xue et al., 2024). The similar structures of anthocyanins with the main variables being different sugars connected to the same common anthocyanidin structures make optimal separation and identification using HPLC-UV almost

impossible. Therefore, to identify and quantify the polyphenols present in both extracts, HPLC-MS/MS analysis was applied (see Section 3.2.).

PCA clusters at all 3 wavelengths for normalized data indicate that the developed HPLC-UV method is suitable for obtaining distinctive fingerprints (Fig. 3). Data clustering based on the first two principal components (PC) was visualized using scatter plots (see Fig. 3), due to the first two PC having explained most of the variance. At 280 nm the first two principal components explained 95 %, at 360 nm 83.6 % and at 520 nm 86.6 % of the total variance. At all three wavelengths, the PC1 separates highbush blueberry extracts from bilberry extracts. The clusters of bilberry extracts are more compact at all three wavelengths, suggesting that the chemical composition of highbush blueberries is more diverse due to the different varieties of this species. The Pearson's correlation coefficients in Table 1 confirm the observations of the PCA score scatter plots since the similarity between samples from one type of plant is lower for highbush blueberry extracts. Interestingly, for both types of extracts, the lowest similarity between samples was seen at 360 nm, indicating that the flavonoid profile differs more between samples than phenolic acid or anthocyanin profiles.

3.2. HPLC-MS/MS phytochemical and chemometric analysis

Due to the high sensitivity and precision of HPLC-MS/MS, which is now state-of-the-art in phytochemical testing, it was applied to determine the phytochemical composition of both extracts. Previous research indicates that anthocyanins, proanthocyanidins, hydroxycinnamic acids, and flavonols are the main groups of phenolics found in blueberry and bilberry extracts (Becker Pertuzatti et al., 2021; Hellstrm et al., 2024; Mustafa et al., 2022; Pico et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021), therefore, the search for tentative compounds was restricted to specifically these groups. Information on a total of 22 identified compounds including their retention time, chemical formula, mass, MS / MS

Fig. 1. Sample assignment to classes in PLS-DA models that contain individual and mixed extracts.

Fig. 2. HPLC-UV chromatograms of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts: (A) Extract chromatograms at 280 nm; (B) Extract chromatograms at 360 nm; (C) Extract chromatograms at 520 nm. Abbreviations: COR – highbush blueberry extract, MYR – bilberry extract.

fragments, and ion mode can be found in [Supplementary data](#), Table S1. All identified compounds were further quantified using HPLC-MS/MS and expressed in mg/g lyophilized extract (see [Table 2](#)).

Only chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid were detected as aglycons; the rest polyphenols were in various glycoside forms (glucosides, galactosides, rutinosides, arabinosides, xylosides, and aldopentosides).

As expected, both extracts analyzed contained a rich profile of anthocyanins. Anthocyanins are the pigments that provide the deep blue, purple, and red color of berries ([Mustafa et al., 2022](#)). Four main anthocyanidin aglycones - cyanidin, delphinidin, malvidin, and peonidin - in glycoside forms, were found in both types of extracts. The

identified anthocyanidins match previous research ([Hellström et al., 2024](#); [Mustafa et al., 2022](#)), however, no petunidin or pelargonidin-based compounds were found in this study. Bilberry extracts contained significantly higher levels of anthocyanins (total anthocyanins 108.1 mg/g of lyophilized extract) compared to highbush blueberry extracts (total anthocyanins 23.5 mg/g of lyophilized extract). High anthocyanin levels in bilberry extracts are explained by the location of anthocyanins in the berries. Bilberries have anthocyanins throughout the whole berry, while highbush blueberries have them only in the skin of the berry ([Riihinen et al., 2008](#)). The size of the highbush blueberry significantly affected the anthocyanin content. Extracts made

Fig. 3. PCA clusters of HPLC-UV fingerprints, normalized data: (A) HPLC-UV, 280 nm; (B) HPLC-UV, 360 nm; (C) HPLC-UV, 520 nm. Abbreviations: COR – highbush blueberry extract, MYR – bilberry extract.

Table 1

Average Pearson correlation coefficients of bilberry and highbush blueberry samples, normalized HPLC-UV, FTIR, and UV/Vis data.

Type of analysis	Pearson correlation coefficient	
	Highbush blueberry extract	Bilberry extract
HPLC-UV 280 nm	0.8928	0.9847
HPLC-UV 360 nm	0.8671	0.9452
HPLC-UV 520 nm	0.9411	0.9856
FTIR	0.9954	0.9939
UV/Vis	0.9970	0.9995

from larger berries contained less anthocyanins due to more pulp compared to skin by weight. Differences between dominant anthocyanins were observed in both types of extracts. The dominant anthocyanidin in bilberry extracts was cyanidin, followed by delphinidin, malvidin, and peonidin, respectively. In contrast, the highest concentration of malvidin was found in highbush blueberry extracts, followed by delphinidin and peonidin with cyanidin in the last place. This coincides with recent studies (Hellström et al., 2024; Pico et al., 2022), except in a study by Hellström et al. in bilberries delphinidin was found to be the main aglycon followed by cyanidin (Hellström et al., 2024). The differences compared to Hellström could be due to different berry processing and extraction methods.

Phenolic acids are another important class of polyphenols commonly found in berry fruits. At detectable concentrations, two hydroxycinnamic acids, caffeic acid and chlorogenic acid, were found in the analyzed samples. Chlorogenic acid (in addition to anthocyanins) was found to be the dominant compound found in highbush blueberry samples. The significant difference in chlorogenic acid content between highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts can be used to identify each product, as highbush blueberry extracts (3.01 ± 1.25 mg/g lyophilized extract) had roughly five times more chlorogenic acid than bilberry extracts (0.69 ± 0.19 mg/g lyophilized extract). This confirms previous research on the high chlorogenic acid content of highbush blueberries (Becker Pertuzatti et al., 2021; Hellström et al., 2024; Mustafa et al., 2022; Pico et al., 2022). The substantially high chlorogenic acid content of highbush blueberries could be responsible for a wide range of biological activity and is worth exploring in the future. The opposite was seen for caffeic acid with bilberry extracts containing two times higher caffeic acid content than highbush blueberry extracts.

Surprisingly, quantifiable concentrations of proanthocyanidins were not found in either type of extract, suggesting that the applied extract preparation method was not suitable to extract these types of compounds.

However, a variety of flavonols were found in both types of extracts. The main flavonols found were myricetin, laricitrin, quercetin, luteolin, isorhamnetin, and kaempferol glycosides. Kaempferol-3-O-galactoside/Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside, quercetin, and rutin were found only in highbush blueberry samples. Laricitrin and quercetin derivatives were found in higher concentrations for highbush blueberry extracts, while

bilberry extracts contained higher concentrations of myricetin and isorhamnetin derivatives. Myricetin-3-O-galactoside/Myricetin-3-O-glucoside was found to be the dominant flavonol compound of bilberry extracts (1.17 ± 0.38 mg/g lyophilized extract). For highbush blueberry extracts, the dominant flavonol was found to be a laricitrin-3-O-aldopentose (0.97 ± 0.25 mg/g lyophilized extract).

Overall, most of the polyphenols identified correspond to previous research on the phytochemical composition of highbush blueberries and bilberries (Becker Pertuzatti et al., 2021; Burdulis et al., 2009; Hellström et al., 2024; Mustafa et al., 2022; Pico et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021). Since in this study, the concentration of compounds was expressed per g of lyophilized extract instead of other measurements such as per gram or kg of fresh or dry weight of fruit, it is hard to compare the quantitative values. The expression per gram of lyophilized extract was chosen because the lyophilized extracts are more likely to be further incorporated into drug delivery systems and applied for pharmaceutical purposes than berries themselves. Since the samples were collected from various places in Latvia, in addition to being collected at different harvests (2022 and 2024), quite a broad range of concentration for each compound was observed, especially for highbush blueberry samples, therefore, enhancing the point that phytochemical profiling, using the fingerprinting method could be more useful than identification/quantification of a single compound.

In terms of chemometric analysis, the PCA clusters of the HPLC-MS/MS data can be found in Fig. 4. The fingerprints highlight that the method optimized for anthocyanin analysis produces more compact clusters of bilberry extracts which contain high concentrations of anthocyanins. Since the polyphenol method focuses on the separation of other polyphenols, not anthocyanins, the bilberry extract cluster is widely scattered. This confirms the need for specific methods for anthocyanin chromatographic analysis due to their similar structures and chemical properties. Overall, with both methods, the explained variance of the first two principal components does not exceed 55 %, indicating the complexity of HPLC-MS/MS fingerprints and the information that they provide.

3.3. FTIR fingerprints and their chemometric analysis

The specific spectra related to the phytochemical composition of these extracts can be seen in the region of 500 to 1800 cm^{-1} , therefore it was determined to be the fingerprint region (Fig. 5A).

The most intense peak was observed in the 1025 – 1040 cm^{-1} region and could represent the C–O vibrations characteristic of carbohydrates (sugars, glycosides, and others) found in fruits (Chen, Zhang, Mujumdar, et al., 2021; Johnson et al., 2022). It is worth mentioning that the bilberry peak (1037 cm^{-1}) is shifted compared to the highbush blueberry peak (1026 cm^{-1}). The peak around 1025 – 1040 cm^{-1} can be used to distinguish between different fruits. A study by Chen et al. confirmed that for blueberries this peak is very distinctive due to the high total sugar content compared to other fruits such as cranberries (Chen, Zhang, Mujumdar, et al., 2021). Before data normalization, for highbush blueberry extracts, this peak had a higher absorbance, indicating that

Table 2
Quantification of the identified compounds in highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts, mean \pm SD.

No.	Tentative compound	Highbush blueberry extract (mg/g lyophilized extract)	Bilberry extract (mg/g lyophilized extract)	Notes
1	Delphinidin-3-O-galactoside	3.62 \pm 1.58	26.05 \pm 4.91	Amount expressed in Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside equivalents
2	Delphinidin-3-O-arabinoside/ Delphinidin-3-O-xyloside	1.93 \pm 0.63	10.37 \pm 1.92	Amount expressed in Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside equivalents
3	Myricetin-3-O-galactoside/ Myricetin-3-O-glucoside	0.56 \pm 0.14	1.17 \pm 0.38	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
4	Cyanidin-3-O-arabinoside/ Cyanidin-3-O-xyloside	0.35 \pm 0.13	9.84 \pm 2.69	Amount expressed in Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside equivalents
5	Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside	0.62 \pm 0.19	32.75 \pm 8.22	
6	Chlorogenic acid	3.01 \pm 1.25	0.69 \pm 0.19	
7	Laricitrin-3-O-aldopentose	0.97 \pm 0.25	0.66 \pm 0.17	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
8	Quercetin-3-O-galactoside/ Quercetin-3-O-glucoside	0.85 \pm 0.24	0.57 \pm 0.11	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
9	Malvidin-3-O-glucoside/ Malvidin-3-O-galactoside	8.91 \pm 2.99	15.54 \pm 4.09	Amount expressed in Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside equivalents
10	Luteolin-7-O-rutinoside/ Kaempferol-3-O-rutinoside	0.01 \pm 0.003	0.05 \pm 0.04	Amount expressed in Kaempferol equivalents
11	Caffeic acid	0.08 \pm 0.04	0.11 \pm 0.03	
12	Malvidin-3-O-arabinoside/ Malvidin-3-O-xyloside	4.60 \pm 1.39	10.18 \pm 3.04	Amount expressed in Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside equivalents
13	Isorhamnetin 3-O-glucoside 7-O-rhamnoside I	0.12 \pm 0.03	0.15 \pm 0.03	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
14	Quercetin-3-(6'-malonyl-glucoside)	0.11 \pm 0.03	0.003 \pm 0.001	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
15	Quercetin-3-O-aldopentose	0.27 \pm 0.14	0.05 \pm 0.02	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
16	Kaempferol-3-O-galactoside/ Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside	0.02 \pm 0.01	NF*	Amount expressed in Kaempferol equivalents
17	Quercetrin	0.13 \pm 0.10	NF	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
18	Peonidin-3-O-arabinoside/ Peonidin-3-O-xyloside	3.51 \pm 0.49	3.39 \pm 0.43	Amount expressed in Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside equivalents

Table 2 (continued)

No.	Tentative compound	Highbush blueberry extract (mg/g lyophilized extract)	Bilberry extract (mg/g lyophilized extract)	Notes
19	Isorhamnetin-3-O-aldopentose	0.15 \pm 0.15	0.03 \pm 0.02	glucoside equivalents Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
20	Isorhamnetin-3-O-galactoside/ Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside	0.17 \pm 0.07	0.61 \pm 0.16	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents
21	Rutin	0.19 \pm 0.09	NF	
22	Laricitrin-3-O-glucoside/ Laricitrin-3-O-galactoside	0.11 \pm 0.06	0.07 \pm 0.03	Amount expressed in Quercetin equivalents

* NF – not found.

highbush blueberry extract contains higher total sugar levels than bilberry extracts.

The peak at 1716 cm^{-1} is related to C=O stretching vibrations, characteristic of anthocyanins (Tarmizi et al., 2019). The peak at 1639 cm^{-1} shows the stretching vibration of the C=C bond of the aromatic group of anthocyanins (Bhushan et al., 2023; Chen, Zhang, Devahastin, et al., 2021; Tao et al., 2017). Additionally, the peak at 1336 cm^{-1} could also be related to aromatic C=C groups of anthocyanins (Bhushan et al., 2023; Tao et al., 2017). It would explain why the peaks at 1716 cm^{-1} , 1639 cm^{-1} , and 1336 cm^{-1} are more intense for bilberry extracts than highbush blueberry extracts since bilberry extracts contain significantly higher levels of anthocyanins. Peaks between 750 and 950 cm^{-1} could be related to the polysaccharides present in the extracts (Chen, Zhang, Devahastin, et al., 2021, 2021). Almost an exact match between the highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts is visible at peaks 814 cm^{-1} and 776 cm^{-1} . In general, the peaks observed in the obtained spectra are comparable to previous studies of highbush blueberry and bilberry samples (Avramia and Amariei, 2022; Chen, Zhang, Devahastin, et al., 2021; Jeyaram and Geethakrishnan, 2020; Kiefer et al., 2016).

Very high similarity expressed as Pearson's correlation coefficients were observed between samples of one type of plant (highbush blueberry 0.9954 (average) and bilberry 0.9949 (average)) and even when comparing both fingerprints one to another (average 0.9920). The similarity between the spectra is probably due to the relatively similar phytochemical composition with compounds having roughly the same functional groups. Although the FTIR spectra can indicate the phytochemical composition of plant extract, the multivariate analysis results indicate that the FTIR method is rather nonspecific and the differences in spectra between two anthocyanin-rich natural products are minimal. This observation is visualized by the PCA clusters (Fig. 5B). Although PC1 allows us to separate most bilberry extracts from highbush blueberry extracts, a wide scattering of highbush blueberry data points is observed.

3.4. UV/Vis fingerprints and their chemometric analysis

UV/Vis spectroscopy is a well-known and commonly used method in phytochemical analysis. It is commonly used to quantify total polyphenol content, total flavonoid content, and others based on colorimetric reactions of certain groups of plant secondary metabolites (Lozada-Ramírez et al., 2021; Shraim et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022). In our study, we proposed to scan the extract in the whole UV/Vis spectra. The region from 195 to 600 nm was chosen as the fingerprinting region (Fig. 6A).

A distinguished peak at 280 nm was observed indicating the presence

Fig. 4. PCA clusters of HPLC-MS/MS fingerprints, normalized data: (A) Polyphenol method; (B) Anthocyanin method. Abbreviations: COR-highbush blueberry extract, MYR – bilberry extract.

Fig. 5. FTIR fingerprints and their PCA clusters of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts: (A) Normalized FTIR spectra (fingerprints); (B) PCA clusters of FTIR fingerprints, normalized data. Abbreviations: COR – highbush blueberry extract, MYR – bilberry extract.

Fig. 6. UV/Vis fingerprints and their PCA clusters of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts: (A) UV/Vis spectra (fingerprints) of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts; (B) PCA clusters of UV/Vis fingerprints, normalized data. Abbreviations: COR – highbush blueberry extract, MYR – bilberry extract.

of phenolic acids and anthocyanins (Fig. 6A). For bilberry extracts, this peak had a higher absorbance possibly due to a higher anthocyanin content, even despite the higher dilution factor. A peak was identified at around 330 nm for highbush blueberry extracts. We hypothesize that the peak is due to chlorogenic acid, since highbush blueberry extracts have a chlorogenic acid content 5 times higher compared to bilberry extracts, based on our HPLC-MS/MS results. Furthermore, chlorogenic acid has an absorption maxima at 330 nm (Guleria et al., 2022). Due to the

extensive dilution, the peak in the region 520 to 560 was very small (not shown); however, since anthocyanins also absorb UV light at around 280 nm (proven by the HPLC-UV method), these spectra were considered acceptable for further analysis. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to publish the UV/Vis spectra of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts. The clustering of the obtained fingerprints can be seen in Fig. 6B. The separation of two clusters indicates that the chosen fingerprinting region is suitable to distinguish between these two types

of extracts. Nevertheless, the UV/Vis method is rather nonspecific, the same as FTIR. It can provide insight into the main groups of secondary plant metabolites present in the extracts, but it cannot be used to identify individual substances in the extracts. The non-specificity of the UV/Vis method is also further proven by Pearson's correlation coefficients – the average coefficient when comparing both extracts was 0.9936, even exceeding the value obtained from FTIR fingerprints.

3.5. Data fusion

Low-level data fusion was applied only to the chromatographic data. Fig. 7 shows the PCA score scatter plots for the low-level fused data. For the HPLC-UV fused data (Fig. 7A), the PC2 separates highbush blueberry from bilberry data. Separate clusters for each type of extract/wavelength were observed, however, clusters of highbush blueberry extracts at 280 nm and 520 nm are less compact than others. Overall, the first two PCs describe 77.6 % of the variance, indicating a good quality of the model.

Fusing all the HPLC-UV and HPLC-MS/MS data using low-level data fusion creates an exceedingly large dataset. The first two PCs explain 67.4 % of the total variance. Interestingly, HPLC-UV bilberry data at 280 nm and 520 nm are clustered together, confirming the initial observation from chromatograms about the anthocyanin's impact on the chromatograms (Fig. 7B). Since HPLC-MS/MS data confirmed the abundance of anthocyanins in bilberry extracts, their clustering together is understandable. The clusters of HPLC-MS/MS data, especially the overall polyphenol method, are overlapping, suggesting that this approach would not be usable to distinguish between both types of extracts. The large amount of data used for the model may be redundant. Instead, extracting key features that explain the clustering of the data may be much more useful, therefore, mid-level data fusion to data from all four analytical techniques was applied.

The data from all four analytical techniques were fused using mid-level data fusion. The initial training dataset was significantly smaller (65 observations, 35 variables) than any of the individual datasets while containing the most important features of the initial data. Two classes – highbush blueberry extracts and bilberry extracts – were assigned to the observations. The PLS-DA analysis revealed R^2Y (cumulative) to be 0.995 and Q^2 (cumulative) to be 0.99, suggesting potential overfitting. Therefore, VIP values were inspected revealing that out of 35 only 7 variables had a VIP value larger than 1 (see Fig. 8).

Interestingly, the seven most important variables were PC1 of each individual dataset. The other variables showed much smaller values with higher SD; therefore, it was decided, that only the 7 variables would be used in the further PLS-DA model. For the new smaller model,

the R^2X (cumulative) was 0.931, R^2Y (cumulative) was 0.983, and Q^2 (cumulative) was 0.981 with the score scatter plot showing better clustering of the classes (Fig. 9A), therefore, this model was deemed successful for further prediction analysis. 10 randomly selected observations (5 for highbush blueberry extracts and 5 for bilberry extracts) were used to predict their belonging to the appropriate class. The prediction was 100 % accurate with all the samples assigned to the appropriate class. The score scatter plot for the prediction set can be seen in Fig. 9B. The correct assignment to classes for the prediction set confirms that the build model can be used to determine the identity of unknown pure bilberry and highbush blueberry extract samples based on the key features extracted from the fingerprints obtained from four different analytical techniques (HPLC-UV, HPLC-MS/MS, FTIR, and UV/Vis).

Previous research on highbush blueberry extracts has applied data fusion and machine learning to hyperspectral imaging systems (Deng et al., 2024; Fan et al., 2018) to characterize different blueberry samples and varieties. No studies on data fusion applied to bilberry products were found. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to successfully apply mid-level data fusion to phytochemical fingerprints obtained by four separate analytical techniques. Previous research has applied data fusion to only spectroscopic data or chromatographic data sources or a mix of only one chromatographic and spectroscopic data source (Zhang and Wang, 2023). The samples were collected in different regions of Latvia during two harvests (2022 and 2024) to maximize natural differences of the samples caused by climate, soil, and growth factors, making the obtained fingerprints, their chemometric analysis, and the built PLS-DA model of pure bilberry and highbush blueberry extracts robust and reliable.

3.6. Chemometric analysis and data fusion of mixed samples

To test if the chosen approach is applicable not only to pure extracts but also to their mixes, the same sequence of procedures was followed. In the PCA analysis, a tendency for mixed samples to cluster together with pure bilberry extracts was observed for both chromatographic and spectroscopic methods. An only exception was the mixed samples that contained highbush blueberry and bilberry extract in a ratio of 80:20. These 80:20 samples formed a separate cluster or tended to group closer to highbush blueberry extracts. This observation is visualized by PCA clusters of HPLC-UV data in Fig. 10.

Therefore, using simple fingerprinting approach using one analytical method is not enough to detect adulteration unless the extract contains 80 % highbush blueberries. Worse, all other types of mixed extracts cluster together with bilberry extract, which is the one often being

Fig. 7. PCA clusters of low-level data fusion: (A) Low-level fused HPLC-UV data; (B) Low-level fused HPLC-UV and HPLC-MS/MS data. Abbreviations: COR HPLC 280 – highbush blueberry extract, HPLC-UV, 280 nm; COR HPLC 360 – highbush blueberry extract, HPLC-UV, 360 nm; COR HPLC 520 – highbush blueberry extract, HPLC-UV, 520 nm; MYR HPLC 280 – bilberry extract, HPLC-UV, 280 nm; MYR HPLC 360 – bilberry extract, HPLC-UV, 360 nm; MYR HPLC 520 – bilberry extract, HPLC-UV, 520 nm; COR MS A – highbush blueberry extract, HPLC-MS/MS, anthocyanin method; COR MS P – highbush blueberry extract, HPLC-MS/MS, polyphenol method; MYR MS A – bilberry extract, HPLC-MS/MS, anthocyanin method; MYR MS P – bilberry extract, HPLC-MS/MS, polyphenol method.

Fig. 8. VIP values of initial PLS-DA analysis, first 12 variables with highest values.

Fig. 9. PLS-DA score scatter plots of mid-level fused data, individual extracts, 1 – highbush blueberry extracts, 2 – bilberry extracts: (A) Training set; (B) Prediction set.

Fig. 10. PCA scatter plots of pure and mixed samples, HPLC-UV, normalized data: (A) HPLC-UV, 280 nm; (B) HPLC-UV, 360 nm; (C) HPLC-UV, 520 nm. Abbreviations: COR – highbush blueberry extract, MYR – bilberry extract.

Table 3
PLS-DA model parameters and their prediction accuracy.

Model type	R ² X (cum.)	R ² Y (cum.)	Q ² (cum.)	Overall prediction accuracy (%)	Number of correctly identified samples (out of 5)		
					Bilberry extracts	Highbush blueberry extracts	Mixed extracts
3 classes	0.950	0.949	0.941	100	5	5	5
5 classes	0.950	0.582	0.473	80	5	5	2
7 classes	0.890	0.390	0.280	73.3	5	5	1

adulterated. In a practical setting this would have serious consequences since adulterated bilberry extracts would be assumed to be pure.

To test if the data fusion approach has an advantage and can be more precise in the detection of potential adulterations, mid-level data fusion was applied with subsequent PLS-DA. The obtained PLS-DA model parameters and prediction accuracy results can be found in Table 3.

The results show that by increasing the number of classes, the explained variance and predictive power decrease significantly. The VIP analysis shows that HPLC-MS/MS data have the highest values and hold the most importance on the models, probably due to the sensitivity of the analytical method. Pure bilberry and highbush blueberry extracts were correctly assigned to their respective classes in all model types. However, all mixed extracts were correctly identified only in the 3-class model. Moreover, only the 3-class model parameters (R^2X , R^2Y , and Q^2) were deemed successful and appropriate.

By applying mid-level data fusion to data of four analytical methods, we can determine if the sample is pure bilberry extract, pure highbush blueberry extract, or an adulterated/mixed sample, but with less certainty determine the composition ratio of the mix. Nevertheless, it is still a significant advantage compared to single stand-alone analytical methods because all adulterations were classified as such in the 3-class model. This approach could be used by regulatory institutions or manufacturers to relatively quickly and cost-efficiently separate adulterated samples from pure samples using fingerprints as a whole without the need to quantify several individual compounds. Moreover, the obtained HPLC-MS/MS data showed that both highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts contain the same principal polyphenols with quite a broad distribution of concentrations due to different geographical origins and harvest years, highlighting the problem with isolated compound quantification and favoring the fingerprint combined with data fusion approach. The proposed model holds potential for future studies, where the accuracy of determining the ratio of mix could potentially be improved further, by training the model using larger sample sizes.

4. Conclusions

Bilberry and highbush blueberry extracts are visually and chemically highly similar with the Pearson correlation coefficients of spectroscopic fingerprints between these two extracts being higher than 0.99. Chromatographic fingerprinting and quantification of polyphenols reveal that chlorogenic acid and anthocyanins are key features impacting the phytochemical profiles of both extracts. However, the high anthocyanin content of highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts significantly impacts and hinders the analysis methods based on UV light absorption. PCA analysis shows that fingerprints from stand-alone analytical methods insufficiently separate mixed samples from pure extracts. Combining fingerprinting information with mid-level data fusion can simplify the model while still accurately representing the key features of phytochemical fingerprints. Moreover, the PLS-DA model with 3 classes built using mid-level fused data allows us to correctly identify pure extracts from mixed extracts. However, even the PLS-DA model cannot fully accurately predict the ratio of which highbush blueberry and bilberry extracts are mixed. This approach should be further tested in the future using other anthocyanin-rich natural products with different extract preparation methods.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ance Bārzdīņa: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization, Visualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing,

Validation, Formal analysis. **Daniela Paula Prudņikova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Methodology. **Marta Žogota:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis. **Baiba Mauriņa:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Dace Bandere:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Project administration. **Agnese Brangule:** Resources, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declarations of competing interest

None

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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